

EUROPEAN

POLICY BRIEF

AI and Citizen Science: Building trust, transparency and hybrid Intelligence

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INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Citizen Science (CS) are increasingly intertwined in the European research and innovation landscape. Both represent collaborative, data-driven approaches to knowledge production, but they differ fundamentally in their relationship to public participation and trust. While AI is often perceived as opaque and centralised, citizen science is rooted in principles of open science, inclusion, and collective agency. Integrating the two offers a path to both creating more efficient and scalable CS initiatives and more democratic, transparent, and human-centred AI systems.

Europe faces an urgent policy challenge: ensuring that AI technologies are developed and governed in ways that reinforce democratic legitimacy and social trust rather than eroding them. The EU AI Act, alongside Horizon Europe's Cluster 2 – Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society, explicitly calls for public engagement and transparency in AI development. Citizen science provides a proven mechanism to achieve this through involving citizens in the co-creation, monitoring, and ethical oversight of AI technologies.

This brief introduces a framing for how to conceive the relationship between AI and Citizen Science (Citizen Science for AI) and leverage AI tools to improve citizen science practice (AI for Citizen Science). It also provides insights into how citizen science projects are currently making use of these technologies, drawing on insights from the IMPETUS Accelerator. Throughout, it highlights the benefits and challenges, as well as providing recommendations for next steps.

While there is no singular definition of AI and Citizen Science, how the two approaches intersect can be defined in two primary ways:

1. **AI for Citizen Science:** Using AI tools to automate and enhance delivery within citizen science projects. This can include using AI throughout a project's lifecycle from proposal writing, through to citizen engagement and analysis or reporting.
2. **Citizen Science for AI:** Engaging citizens through citizen science in the creation, auditing, and ethical evaluation of AI systems to ensure fairness, transparency, and accountability.

Both approaches share a commitment to openness and co-creation. Together, they exemplify a new paradigm of collective intelligence, where humans and machines collaborate to generate knowledge that is socially informed and democratically governed.

Key methodologies emerging in this space include:

1. **Hybrid Human-AI Workflows:** Combining algorithmic pre-processing with human verification to optimise accuracy.
 - One of the most prominent examples of this is the [Zooniverse](#), [Galaxy Zoo](#) initiative. Here, AI models trained on volunteer classifications pre-sort astronomical images, allowing human participants to focus on ambiguous or novel findings. This partnership between human insight and algorithmic efficiency accelerates discovery and maintains engagement through shared agency.
 - Another example is the [iNaturalist project](#), where AI-powered image recognition tools assist volunteers in identifying biodiversity observations in real time. This both helps increase participation and improve data accuracy and coverage.
2. **Participatory Data Governance:** Involving communities in decisions about data ownership, consent, and reuse.
 - ["The Call"](#) was an exhibition and participatory data project by Berlin-based artists Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst. They proposed a voice AI trained on the voices of choristers. To collect data, the artists composed a songbook for fifteen community choirs across the UK. The choristers also participated in a [Choral Data Trust experiment](#), collaboratively defining the governance framework for the use of their training data and the resulting AI model.
 - [DeepTime](#) is a citizen science platform with thousands of contributors mapping heritage and ecology run by Dig Ventures. They are involving their volunteers in deciding the governance processes for their data platform. Their aim is to create a data commons where communities retain meaningful control over data they help create, ensuring technology serves local environmental needs.

3. **Algorithmic Co-creation:** Citizens helping to design or train AI models, particularly in underrepresented language, societal or cultural contexts.
 - One example of using CS to inform the design of algorithms is the [Masakhane Project](#). A grassroots citizen science initiative that trains natural language models for African languages, addressing data inequality and broadening the use and diversity of languages in AI systems.
 - Exploring a similar challenge, [Indigenous Protocols and AI Lab](#), has set up a collaborative initiative between technologists and Indigenous communities that use participatory research to embed cultural values and ethical norms into the design of AI solutions.

4. **Deliberative AI Oversight:** Citizen panels, deliberative polling or juries are used to evaluate the ethics, social impacts, and fairness of AI deployment.
 - **Public AI Task Force:** Nesta's Centre for Collective Intelligence conducted public deliberations where people voted on which AI tools are acceptable for use in the UK's public sector. The Centre designed a process known as the AI Social Readiness Assessment, where members of the public (the Public AI Task Force) learn about a specific AI tool, how it works, including its potential benefits and risks. The groups then develop practical guidelines for public sector organizations and AI developers on how to use these tools responsibly and for the public good.

Systemic benefits: From data ethics to policy innovation

When combined, AI and CS form a hybrid intelligence ecosystem that can deliver distinct systemic benefits:

- **Transparency:** Shared data governance models ensure visibility into how algorithms operate and whose knowledge informs them.
- **Equity:** Participatory datasets reduce bias and expand cultural representation in training data.
- **Democratic legitimacy:** AI developed through open, participatory processes enjoys higher public trust and greater policy durability.

These benefits directly align with Europe's strategic objectives under Horizon Europe and the Digital Europe Programme, fostering responsible, human-centred, and trustworthy AI ecosystems.

Over the last cohort of the IMPETUS Accelerator, we documented the reported uses of AI by our projects. During this period, generative AI tools such as chatGPT, Claude, Gemini and Co-pilot have become increasingly ubiquitous. We found a range of uses from routine administrative support to sophisticated data analysis and participant-led digital engagement, alongside a notable undercurrent of methodological caution.

1. Routine Administration, Translation, and Communication

The most prevalent use of generative AI is as a digital assistant for operational and communication tasks. Numerous projects reported using tools like ChatGPT to refine English phrasing, adjust text formality, and overcome language barriers.

- For instance, the *NEYSA project* used LLMs to translate or check materials, while the *Unique* project relied on AI translation when bilingual personnel were unavailable.
- AI is also used to adapt scientific outputs for public audiences - the *Disaster Risk* and *GV-CLIMA* projects used ChatGPT to tailor social media messaging to specific demographics.
- Several projects, including *Living Soils Lab* and *CollFacts* used automated transcription for focus groups and communication videos.

2. Ideation and Protocol Development

Several projects use generative AI to navigate bureaucratic bottlenecks and structure early-stage research.

- *Waste-Free Wantage* successfully used an LLM to draft provisional survey structures required for a university ethics application, which later informed their participatory co-design sessions.
- Similarly, *Waste to Wealth* used ChatGPT to outline an experimental protocol and summarise literature, though the research team was careful to double-check all AI-generated outlines against scientific literature.

3. Data Analysis and Custom Tooling

While many projects restrict AI to text generation, a small subset have used generative AI for data processing or developing customised deployments.

- The *Observatory* project in Spain applied Gemini, Copilot, and ChatGPT to process vast amounts of qualitative citizen narratives; they extract geographic coordinates, detect hate speech, attempt sentiment analysis, and even simulate population segments using AI personas to test communication campaigns.
- In the *Regenerative Tides* project, a participant developed a custom "bad boats GPT" programmed with scientific guardrails to provide the public with accurate information on marine pollution.

4. Participant-Led Digital Participation

In certain projects, AI is an active tool placed directly in the hands of volunteers and participants.

- The *City Layers* project asked school children to use generative AI (such as Gemini) to create visualisations of their suggested urban improvements, and the team is currently prototyping a conversational, AI-driven mapping tool.
- The integration of AI into everyday digital participation was highlighted by the *CollFacts* project - an initiative studying how the public navigates misinformation - which discovered that multi-generational participants, including 80-year-olds, were independently using AI to fact-check folk sayings during workshops.

Methodological Caution: Despite the utility of these digital tools, we also noted that several projects intentionally avoided or limited their use of AI due to ethical concerns. The reasons given by project teams included issues with data privacy risks and concerns that AI tools often pull from biased, outdated sources and fail to produce universally inclusive outputs.

BARRIERS TO RESPONSIBLE AI AND POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS

Despite promising pilots, better integration of AI and Citizen Science (CS) presents significant methodological and ethical hurdles that must be addressed to ensure these technologies serve the public good.

1. Low awareness of data bias and exclusion: A significant knowledge gap exists regarding how AI can perpetuate biases or exclude specific demographics, often due to pulling from outdated or non-inclusive sources. To mitigate this, practitioners should prioritise the creation of participatory datasets through open, community-led infrastructures. This would help ensure that training data is more representative of diverse linguistic, cultural, and geographic contexts and help to raise awareness about the limitations of these tools.

2. Lack of transparency in AI systems: The ‘black box’ nature of many AI technologies can erode social trust and hinder democratic legitimacy particularly if models are used to provide analysis within projects that have significant public interest or social impact. To address this opacity, dedicated EU programs should be established to support the development of open-source models. More emphasis on algorithmic accountability for funded projects could further ensure that the logic behind AI-driven decisions remains visible to the public.

3. Skill and literacy gaps: There is a documented need for increased capacity among both the researchers deploying these tools and the volunteers interacting with them. Funding should be directed toward training on AI literacy and participatory data practices for citizen scientists. Established European citizen science networks such as the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) should invest in developing these resources to build cross-sectoral capability and foster a culture of responsible innovation.

4. Ethical and legal uncertainties: The integration of AI into data-driven research often outpaces current regulatory clarity, leading to concerns regarding data privacy and consent. Establishing formal EU guidelines for participatory data ethics and consent management would provide the necessary safeguards for citizen rights. Furthermore, adopting participatory governance models, like the Nesta’s Public AI Task Force, can help projects navigate these complexities while enhancing ethical compliance.

For EU and National Funders

- **Mainstream AI and citizen science integration:** Embed AI-enabled citizen science in Horizon Europe, Digital Europe, and the New European Bauhaus. Create funding calls specifically linking AI ethics and participatory governance.
- **Invest in data equity:** Fund participatory dataset creation and community-led data stewardship projects, prioritising linguistic, cultural, and geographic diversity to help make these projects open source and freely accessible.
- **Support open and explainable AI:** Mandate transparency and algorithmic accountability for AI systems funded through EU research programmes. Open these up for research through citizen science based approaches.

For Institutions using AI and CS

- **Adopt Participatory AI governance:** Establish citizen panels or advisory boards to oversee AI projects, enhancing legitimacy and compliance with ethical standards.
- **Build skills and capacity:** Develop tailored training for researchers and citizen scientists to understand the potential of AI tools and its risks to foster shared understanding and responsible innovation.

For Practitioners and Researchers

- **Design for co-creation:** Develop hybrid workflows which optimise for human and algorithmic complementarity. Involve volunteers and communities in decisions about how AI is integrated into the project.
- **Document ethical impact:** Evaluate AI+CS projects using metrics of social value, inclusion, and trust, not only efficiency or accuracy.
- **Scale good practice:** Share experiences, what works and what doesn't openly to accelerate replication across Europe's research and innovation ecosystem, working with established networks like ECSA.

PROJECT NAME

IMPETUS

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WEBSITE

<https://impetus4cs.eu/>

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